

Declaration of interest: None

Heat collection in an attached sunspace

María José Suárez López^{a*}, Silvia Soutullo Castro^b, Antonio Navarro Manso^a, Eduardo Blanco Marigorta^a

^aUniversidad de Oviedo, EDZE (Energía), Campus de Viesques, 33203 Gijón (Asturias) Spain.

^bCIEMAT, Energy Efficiency in Buildings Unit, Adva Complutense, 28040 Madrid Spain.

*Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 985182114.

E-mail address: suarezlmaria@uniovi.es (M.J. Suárez).

Abstract

The attached sunspaces are classic bioclimatic systems. Normally, they are used as solar passive techniques in buildings. However, it has been suggested that they could also be used as active systems in order to collect solar energy and harness it in the heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) equipment. This paper analyses the sunspace built during the ARFRISOL project, which has a validated simulation tool of its thermal behaviour, developed in a previous research. In this paper, this tool is applied to study the possibility of the energy collection. Although this energy is not enough to be used as direct heating system, it can pre-heat the air before entering the HVAC equipment. Two configurations have been studied: collecting the energy during the whole day or only at night to take advantage of the sunspace thermal inertia. Also, the results obtained with these configurations have been compared with the sunspace used in passive mode. For this analysis, several characteristic days with summer and winter climatic conditions have been considered. Finally, an economic evaluation of this innovative system –a solar active sunspace- is performed taking into account the results of the different configurations.

Keywords: Sunspace, CFD, Energy-efficient building, Solar passive design, Heat collection, Economical evaluation.

1. Introduction

In recent years, energy efficiency and passive solar design have become essential features in modern buildings (new or renovated) in order to reduce their high-energy consumption [1-3]. One of these passive solar solutions is the attached sunspace (or greenhouse). It can be considered as a –in façade– solar heating system with thermal inertia. The usual design of these systems is a room with an exterior wall wholly glazed and facing south (north in the southern hemisphere), and a partially glazed interior wall connecting the sunspace with the main building. The space between both walls is relatively wide because, in the bioclimatic architecture concept, it is designed to collect the solar radiation energy on the floor. Sometimes, in order to accumulate this thermal energy the floor has a thick layer of sand or gravel, acting as a thermal mass.

This paper describes and analyses the thermal characteristics of a sunspace built during the ARFRISOL (Bioclimatic Architecture and Solar Cooling) project, organized and promoted by the Spanish Education and Science Authority. This Strategic Singular Project has studied the energy behaviour of five demonstration-containers, located in different climatic conditions. The aim was to demonstrate that it is possible to reduce the conventional energy consumption and the consequent

31 emissions in more than 80% by combining both passive (sunspace, ventilated façade, glass corridor, etc.) and active (solar
32 collector, photovoltaic, geothermal, biomass) energy systems [4]. One of these demonstration-containers has been built in
33 Asturias (northern of Spain) and it has, among other bioclimatic solutions, the sunspace studied in this paper (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Attached sunspace in demonstration-container located in the north of Spain viewed from the exterior.

34
35 In this case, the exterior of the sunspace is a glazed wall, with transparent simple glass in the central stripe and semi-
36 transparent photovoltaic panels on both the upper and lower parts. The floor of the interior space is composed of sand and a
37 partially glazed wall partition separates the sunspace from the hall and meeting room. On the top of this interior partition,
38 there are some grilles in order to provide a possible connection with the air ducts and the heating, ventilation and air
39 conditioning (HVAC) equipment (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Interior of the attached sunspace.

40

41 The passive thermal behaviour of this sunspace was analysed in a previous study [5], where a numerical model was
42 developed and validated using experimental tests made during the ARFRISOL project. The study confirmed that the sand at
43 the floor is a good inertia element, collecting the solar radiation as thermal energy, and releasing this stored energy to the
44 interior air, not only during the daylight hours but also during the night. The analysis of the sand and air temperatures showed
45 that there was a fair amount of heat transfer, mainly during the coldest seasons, although the highest temperature differences
46 were found in spring and autumn, even more than in winter. The effect in summer is somewhat dampened due to the bigger
47 shadowed area, as a consequence of the sun elevation.

48 In this paper, the numerical model has been used to analyse the sunspace as an active energy system. This is an innovative
49 application of sunspaces (and even glazed spaces in general), that has been suggested [6,7], but has not been properly
50 developed. The objective is both to evaluate the possibility of collecting the thermal energy stored and use this energy for the
51 heating of the building during the winter season. Although the system has not been fully implemented, the sunspace has a
52 grille in a lateral wall allowing the entry of outside air, and several grilles in the interior wall, which can be connected to the
53 HVAC system. It has been found that the air temperature in the sunspace in winter does not rise enough to be used as a direct
54 heating system, but it can be utilised, for example, to pre-heat the air employed for renovation by the HVAC equipment. This
55 arrangement has been studied with two configurations: collecting the air during the whole day or only during the night. The
56 second configuration should benefit from the thermal inertia, using the available energy when the outside air is colder.

57 Both configurations have been simulated with the numerical model, for different specific days, and the energy collected has
58 been calculated. In addition, an economic evaluation has been performed to compare the energy savings with the construction
59 costs.

60 The novelty of this article is mainly the solar active use of the sunspace, but also the energy calculations in the sunspace are
61 meaningful because the quantitative analysis of glazed spaces available in the scientific literature have been made almost
62 exclusively in smaller spaces, basically glazed galleries (or balconies). The studies of full scale installations are scarce as well,
63 and even more those containing elements of inertia. Furthermore, it is distinctive the precise evaluation of the investment
64 recovery.

65 **2. Literature review**

66 The solar passive heating systems (Trombe walls, glazed spaces, sunspaces...) help to reduce the conventional energy used
67 to heat the buildings [2,8,9]. The most used are the glazed spaces, ranging from a narrow corridor to a wide hall, with or
68 without thermal mass. They have been widely studied and their thermal performance has been analysed using numerical or
69 thermal simulations and experimental data. Some authors only point out the energy efficiency of these solutions, giving some

70 recommendations on the use of these elements to reduce the loads of the buildings [1,10]. In other papers, the energy savings
71 are explicitly calculated. These values vary in function of the climatic conditions among other variables. For example, Suárez
72 et al., [11] study a glazed gallery located in the northern Spain (Asturias), which can obtain between 15% and 32% of the
73 energy required to heat the adjacent local. Monge-Barrio and Sánchez-Ostiz [2] analyse different balconies in several
74 locations of Spain and they find that the general thermal conditioning demand can be reduced 50% as an average (up to 67%
75 in zones with cold winters). Hilliaho et al., [7] study the impact of different types of glazed balconies on the energy
76 consumption of a building located in Finland, where the energy saving potential is typically about 9% (although the maximum
77 value can be 30%).

78 Regarding the sunspaces, there are several general studies that analyse the thermal performance of these solutions. They
79 usually employ analytical or numerical methods (such as TRNSYS) to show that the sunspaces can be very effective mainly in
80 winter [12,13]. Some of these analysis include comparisons with experimental data as Chen and Liu [14], who use a
81 laboratory scale model or Mottard and Fisore [15] with a full-scale prototype.

82 There are studies where energy savings are calculated, usually for specific locations. Bakos [16] studies a sunspace located
83 in northern Greece and states that the annual electricity savings can be around 80%. Bataineh and Fayed [17] study
84 numerically the thermal performance of a sunspace located in Jordan and they find that, combining the sunspace and passive
85 cooling techniques, the annual heating and cooling loads can be reduced around 42%. Ignjatovic et al., [6] show that for the
86 climate characteristics of Belgrade, a big impact on energy consumption (about 1.9 MWh annual reduction) is achieved with a
87 sunspace with average glazing solar coefficient and part of the sunspace envelope opened for ventilation.

88 Papers about sunspaces with an enhanced inertia element are scarce. Chen and Liu [14] analyse the heat transfer and the
89 airflow in a room at laboratory scale, with a sunspace and a heat storing system in the floor in winter conditions. Olivetti et al.,
90 [18] study a sunspace with a vertical heat storage system. Owraq et al., [3] analyse the thermal performance of a sunspace
91 located in Iran, including heat-storing porous floor bed and water tanks. Typically, these studies show that the heat storing
92 systems improve the energy efficiency and the comfort of the sunspace, increasing the energy savings.

93 Referring to the economic evaluation, there are not many papers. Roach and Kirschner [19] present an economic study of
94 an attached sunspace in a single-family house, taking into account the building cost and the conventional energy price
95 (specifically, natural gas and electricity). They mention that in some cases the recovery of the investment can be achieved in a
96 short period of time. Bakos and Tsagas [20] make an economic analysis of an attached sunspace located in northern Greece.
97 They also state that the energy savings achieved with this system allow recovering the investment in a few years. However,

98 the main factor in these calculations is usually the building cost, for example, Owraq et al., [3] who evaluate the over cost of
99 the sunspace as 5% of total construction cost, found that the recovery time could be up to 20 years.

100 Finally, several authors point out the overheating problem of the sunspaces during the summer, and how it can be reduced
101 using different passive cooling techniques. Most of them show that a proper ventilation and shading devices can be effective
102 methods, decreasing the temperature inside the sunspace considerably [2,21]. Bataineh and Fayed [17] propose night
103 ventilation and interior curtains and check that these techniques significantly reduce the annual cooling loads. Ignjatovic et al.
104 [6] simulate various scenarios varying the percentage of openings and the shading coefficient of glazing, looking for an
105 equilibrium between heating and cooling loads. Mihalakakou [13] considers that these techniques are not enough and
106 complements them with buried pipes. None of these practices completely eliminates the problem, but they are usually
107 adequate for the sunspace to be successfully used throughout the year.

108 3. Methodology

109 In this study, the numerical model developed using the CFD code ANSYS 12.1, and validated in [5], will be utilized. This
110 code allows the simultaneous analysis of fluid movement and heat transfer problems, solving the Navier-Stokes equations
111 (including the energy equation), with the finite volumes method.

112 A three-dimensional geometry with the same dimensions as the real sunspace was solved, including the shape in S of the
113 partially glazed interior partition.

114 An unstructured mesh was created with triangular prism cells, not only for the fluid zones, but also for the solid materials
115 (opaque and semitransparent). A detail of this grid (with 1,000,000 cells) is shown in Fig. 3.

116 Turbulent effects were included using a k-epsilon approach (RNG) [22], including buoyancy effects.

Fig. 3. Attached sunspace in demonstration-container located in the north of Spain viewed from the exterior.

117 In the sunspace a large part of the heat transfer takes place by radiation. The Discrete Ordinates model [23] has been
118 chosen to determine its effects, because it can simulate the radiation through semi-transparent materials, such as glass. In
119 addition, it allows visible radiation to be differentiated from infrared radiation. For this purpose, two bands were defined,
120

121 characterized by the wavelength interval (visible radiation waveband from 0.4 to 2.9 mm; infrared radiation waveband from
122 2.9 to 1000 mm) and by the radiation absorption coefficients for the semi-transparent materials.

123 The fluid circulating in the sunspace is air, and an ideal gas behaviour is assumed for the calculation of the density and to
124 take into account the buoyancy effects. Regarding the solid materials, the floor and the roof are simulated as a homogenous
125 concrete slab, with a sand layer of 30 cm on the top of the floor.

126 With respect to the rest of the boundary and simulation conditions:

- 127 • Convection and radiation have been taken into account on the glazed surfaces at the contour of the domain. Following
128 UNE-EN-673, the heat convection coefficients were defined as $23 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ for the outer side of the exterior glazing and
129 $8 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ for the glazing in the partition wall.
- 130 • The radiation on the interior glazing was considered using the ambient temperature as the external black body
131 temperature.
- 132 • For the radiation on the exterior glazing, experimental data have been used together with variables calculated by the
133 ASHRAE method as explained in [5].
- 134 • According to the current regulations for buildings in Spain [24], the interior air temperature was considered 21°C in
135 winter conditions and 26°C in summer. The exterior air temperature was measured in situ.
- 136 • About the air inflow and outflow, a constant pressure was used for the incoming airflow, while the outgoing airflow had
137 a constant velocity boundary condition.

138 The air temperature, the sun position and solar radiation, both direct and diffuse, were set using a User-Defined Function
139 (UDF). It was developed in C and compiled to integrate it in the CFD code.

140 About the factors affecting the accuracy of the results, a second order discretization was applied for the equations, and the
141 convergence criterion was that the normalised values of all the residuals were lower than 10^{-5} . To ensure the residuals were
142 below the reference values, the number of iterations were fixed at 80 by time step.

143 These calculations have been made for a characteristic day in each season. The selected days are the fifteenth of March,
144 June, September and December. To obtain the results on these days, unsteady simulations have been performed, setting the
145 time step at 5 minutes, resulting in 288 time steps per day.

146 In this part of the research, to study the heat collection, an airflow was imposed from the grille at the exterior lateral wall to
147 the grilles on the top of the interior wall. The air speed was fixed by the rated renovation value of the HVAC equipment (500
148 m^3/h). The air enters the sunspace at the exterior temperature and the temperature of the outgoing air is one of the results
149 obtained in the simulations.

150 With these simulations, data have been obtained for three different arrangements: collecting the air during the whole day,
151 collecting only during the night, and without air collection. The last configuration does not retrieve any energy, but it is the
152 passive mode reference state.

153 4. Heat collection results

154 4.1. Qualitative analysis

155 First, a qualitative analysis of the thermal and fluid-dynamic variables is carried out, using the first configuration:
156 collecting the air during the whole day. As an example, Fig. 4 shows the temperature contours in a cross section, situated two
157 meters away from the exterior glazing for a typical spring day: 15 March at 11 am. It can be observed that the sand surface and
158 the opaque walls are hotter than the air, due to the direct impact of the solar radiation. The higher temperatures in the opaque
159 zones produce the convective movements, which prevent the thermal stratification and maintain the air temperature fairly
160 uniform throughout the section. The mean air temperature is 16°C approximately, 6°C higher than the exterior temperature. As
161 it is relatively early in the day, it can also be seen that most of the sand mass is cold and only the upper layer has started to
162 heat.

Fig. 4. Temperature contours in a cross section of the sunspace, located two meters away from the exterior glazing; 15 March at 11 am, solar irradiation 597.43 W/m², exterior temperature 9.8°C; configuration: sunspace used as a direct heating system collecting air during the whole day.

163
164 As regards the air path within the sunspace, the stream lines on 15 March at 11 am and at midnight (with and without solar
165 radiation) are plotted in Fig. 5. These lines start at the inlet grille and are coloured with the air temperature. The flow moves
166 towards the exterior glazing quickly, and from there, in an encircling movement, it proceeds to sweep the floor and ceiling. In
167 Fig. 5 a, with solar radiation, it can be seen clearly that the air is heated in contact with the glazing, especially in the upper and
168 lower parts, where the photovoltaic modules are installed. The air is hotter in these zones due to the higher opacity and the
169 heat generated by the photovoltaic cells in the energy transformation process. Also, it can be observed that the air flow is
170 heated in contact with the sand, and it is partly cooled in contact with the ceiling. These temperature differences generate
171 currents, which cause quite a chaotic flow in the central volume of the sunspace. When there is no radiation, Fig. 5b, the flow
172 is very similar to the previous situation, but in this case, the glazing is cold and the air flow is heated in contact with the floor,

173 ceiling and walls. The air flow in the interior of the volume maintains a more uniform temperature and it is proportionally
174 colder than in the previous case. It can be supposed that for this reason there is less turbulence.

Fig. 5. Stream lines coming out from the grille and coloured with the air temperature; (a) 15 March at 11 am, solar irradiation 597.43 W/m², exterior temperature 9.8°C; (b) 15 March at midnight, without solar irradiation, exterior temperature 5.5°C; configuration in both cases: sunspace used as a direct heating system collecting air during the whole day.

175 To summarize the qualitative analysis, it can be seen that during the day the glazing and sand are the zones with the higher
176 heat transference. Also, when there is no solar radiation the glazing stops heating, whereas the sand maintains its temperature.
177 About the other days studied, the behaviour of the flow is basically the same, although there are some differences regarding
178 the temperature values.

179 4.2. Quantitative analysis

180 The most important results obtained are the temperatures of the air, sand, etc. throughout the whole day, which are
181 basically function of the solar radiation and the exterior temperature. In this quantitative analysis, the temperatures in the
182 selected days are studied, beginning with the passive mode configuration (without heat recovery), considering it as a
183 reference.

184 Fig. 6 presents the thermal behaviour of the sunspace without heat collection, in the passive mode, throughout the day on
185 15th December. It shows the solar radiation, both average and surface temperature of the sand and both exterior and interior
186 air temperature. During the daylight, all temperatures are very influenced by the solar radiation. But, at night the sand acts as
187 an inertia element, releasing the heat stored during the day. This effect has two phases. First, the upper layer of the sand,
188 whose temperature is quite higher than the average, releases the heat in the evening (from 4 to 8 pm), extending the high
189 temperatures produced by the solar radiation. Then, the heat stored in the bulk of the sand is released in a much more

190 progressive way throughout the night, maintaining the interior air temperature substantially above the exterior one. This
 191 behaviour of the sand as inertia element has been studied in [5], including the variation of the temperature inside the sand.

Fig. 6. Solar irradiation, mean temperature of the sand, surface temperature of the sand and both exterior and interior air temperature throughout the day on 15th December; configuration: sunspace used in the passive mode.

192 This behaviour is basically the same all around the year with differences due to the exterior temperature and the amount of
 193 solar radiation received. Fig. 7 presents the interior air temperature throughout the day for each day simulated (15th March,
 194 June, September and December), maintaining the same configuration (passive mode). In this figure, the effect of the exterior
 195 temperature and the solar radiation reaching the sunspace can be evaluated. The average value is mainly related with the
 196 exterior temperature, being between 5°C and 10°C higher approximately. The highest increase of the air temperature over the
 197 mean value happens in December; this increase is lower in March, then in September and finally in June. This is due to the
 198 sun angle and the shading of the roof, which makes the solar radiation effect be effectively larger in winter than in summer.
 199

Fig. 7. Interior air temperature throughout all the day for each day simulated (15th March, June, September and December), using the sunspace in the passive mode.

201 When the sunspace is used to collect the thermal energy, the interior air does not reach temperatures as high as in the
 202 passive mode, especially during the night. Also, the sand temperature is lower, but the difference is smaller than with the air.
 203 An example of these results is shown in Fig. 8. This figure presents the solar radiation, both inside and outside temperatures
 204 and the surface and mean sand temperatures, on 15th December collecting the air during the whole day.

205 At night, the mean temperature of the sand is 8.61°C in this configuration, while this value is 8.90°C in passive mode. In
 206 spite of the lower values of the temperatures, they are between 3°C and 4°C above the exterior air temperature. The behaviour
 207 of the interior air is very similar. At night, the mean temperature of the interior air is approximately 5.7°C, whereas in passive
 208 mode this value is 8.5°C. About the maximum temperature of the air, in this configuration, the value is 11.09°C, while it is
 209 13.55°C when the sunspace works as a passive system. In this configuration, with a flow rate of 500 m³/h, a thermal power of
 210 about 600 W is collected.

Fig. 8. Solar radiation, both inside and outside temperatures and the surface and mean sand temperatures, on 15th December; configuration: collecting the air during the whole day.

211
 212 In this case, unlike the passive mode (Fig. 6), the temperature of the sand surface is always higher than the interior air one.
 213 So, if night prevalence is wanted, the air could be collected only during the night, allowing a higher heating of the sand during
 214 the daylight hours, in order to obtain more thermal power at night. This option is studied in Fig. 9, which shows the inside air
 215 temperature in all configurations: passive mode, collecting the air during the whole day and only during the night, on 15th
 216 December. It can be seen that when the air is collected only at night, during daylight the temperature inside is practically the
 217 same as in the passive configuration. And, at night, this temperature is approximately the same in both configurations
 218 collecting the air during the whole day and only at night. This suggests that the partial night collection is not much more
 219 effective than the whole day one.

Fig. 9. Exterior air temperature and interior air temperature for all configurations: passive mode, collecting the air during the whole day or only during the night, on 15th December.

220

221 In order to detail the energy collected, it has been calculated for each day simulated (15th March, June, September and
 222 December), for both configurations: collecting the air during the whole day or only at night (Table 1). For example, with
 223 respect to Fig. 9, the energy collected on 15th December, at night is 6606 Wh, when the air is collected during the whole day.
 224 Whereas if the air is collected only at night, the energy is only a bit higher, 7192 Wh. This indicates that there is not much
 225 more energy stored in this configuration. When the air is collected during the whole day, the energy is 7018 Wh during the
 226 daylight. It would be expected that, if the air is only collected at night, the energy during the daylight got stored in the sand,
 227 and that the energy collected at night increased substantially. But the data show that it is not true, this energy only increases
 228 10%. So, the diurnal energy not collected is mainly lost. The same has been found for the other characteristic days.

Table 1. Energy collected for each day simulated (15th March, June, September and December), for two configurations: collecting the air during the whole day or only at night.

Configuration	Collecting air during the whole day	Collecting air at night
March	Energy (Wh)	Energy (Wh)
Daylight	6102	--
Night	8662	9015
Total	14764	9015
June	Energy (Wh)	Energy (Wh)
Daylight	1985	--
Night	1786	1944
Total	3771	1944
September	Energy (Wh)	Energy (Wh)
Daylight	3667	--
Night	5205	5417
Total	8872	5417
December	Energy (Wh)	Energy (Wh)
Daylight	7018	--
Night	6606	7192
Total	13624	7192

229

230 Regarding the data in March, the energy collected during the whole day is 14764 Wh, whereas if the air is collected only at
231 night, this value is 9015 Wh. Comparing March and December, the energy collected in March is higher, 8% during the whole
232 day and 25% only at night, because the hours of solar radiation and the exterior air temperature are greater.

233 In June, very little energy is collected –3184 Wh during the whole day, and 1944 Wh at night–, even though the exterior air
234 temperature is low. This is mainly due to the sun elevation. In September (considering this month as an average of three
235 summer months), the sunspace is not a good solution during the daylight because the ambient temperatures are relatively high
236 and there is no need for heating. The system is only useful at night, although the energy that could be collected during the
237 daylight is not negligible.

238 Considering the days analysed as representative, if the air is collected only at night and the data are extrapolated throughout
239 the year, the total energy collected will be 2169.75 kWh. Whereas, if the air is collected during the whole day only in March,
240 June and December and at night in September, the energy obtained will be 4622.67 kWh (more than twice higher).

241 *4.3. Economical evaluation*

242 This analysis demonstrates that an attached sunspace similar to this one could substantially contribute to save energy and
243 therefore, to preserve the environment. However, translating this saving into money, there are many factors to be considered,
244 such as the dimensions of the adjacent rooms and the sunspace, their insulation and the price of the energy used. To give a
245 comprehensive conclusion, a comparison has been made employing the customary building specifications for this location
246 (north of Spain).

247 The cost of a normally-built sunspace has been offered by a local builder at around 700 €/m². This sunspace has a surface
248 of 50 m², so its cost would be 34650 €. The heat collected in the sunspace throughout the year was between 2170 kWh and
249 4623 kWh depending on the configuration. If the energy used is electricity, whose price is about 0.15 €/kWh nowadays, the
250 saving would be between 325.50 and 693.45 €/year, respectively.

251 If the extra insulation provided by the sunspace is also considered, this saving is even higher. In order to perform an
252 approximate calculation of this insulation, it can be assumed that the temperature in the sunspace is on average around 3.5°C
253 above the exterior temperature, considering that the interior partition has an overall heat transfer coefficient of 4.40 W/m²·K
254 and a surface of 40 m², the energy loss would be 955 kWh less per year approximately. If the electricity is used as energy
255 source, this saving is about 143.21 € per year. Taking into account these possible savings, recovering the sunspace investment
256 would take at least 41 years. In addition, other uses of the sunspace can be taken into account, such as leisure, aesthetic
257 reasons and so on. However, the economic value of this last consideration is difficult to measure.

258 The previous calculations have not taken into account the increase in the asset value of the property. This increase is quite
259 difficult to evaluate due to the applicable legal rules mainly concerning the habitability. However, if the sunspace can be
260 considered as a liveable space, the property gain is usually higher than the construction cost.

261 **6. Conclusions**

262 In this paper, the sunspace built during the ARFRISOL project has been analysed by using a validated simulation tool for
263 the study of its thermal behaviour. In order to evaluate the possibility of collecting the solar energy and to use it in the HVAC
264 system, a characteristic day in each season has been selected: the fifteenth of March, June, September and December. And
265 three possible configurations of this sunspace have been studied: passive mode, collecting the energy during the whole day
266 and collecting the energy only at night.

267 Regarding the results, both qualitative and quantitative studies have been performed. In the first one, the temperature
268 distribution and the air path lines within the sunspace with and without radiation have been analysed. It has been seen that
269 during the daylight the glazing and sand were the zones with the higher heat transference. When there was no solar radiation,
270 the glazing stopped heating, whereas the sand maintained its temperature. In the quantitative analysis, the thermal behaviour
271 of this sunspace has been determined varying its configuration –passive mode, collecting the air during the whole day or only
272 at night– and evaluating the effect of the exterior temperature and solar radiation. Furthermore, the effect of the sand inertia
273 has been emphasised distinguishing between the values of the sand surface temperature and the mean ones. It has been found
274 that the inertia effect is quite important because it allows to collect energy throughout the night, but at the same time it is
275 limited because it cannot store much more energy if it is not collected during the daylight hours.

276 Finally, the energy collected has been calculated throughout the year considering both configurations: collecting the air
277 only at night or during the whole day. In the first configuration, the annual energy is 2.2 MWh, whereas in the second
278 configuration, this value is 4.6 MWh (more than twice higher). Translating this energy collection into money and considering
279 the electricity as the energy used, the economic saving can be between 325 and 693 €/year, respectively. If also the extra
280 insulation provided by the sunspace is considered, then this saving will be increased in about 143 € per year. Taking into
281 account the cost of a normally-built sunspace, its dimensions, the current price of the electricity and the possible savings, the
282 sunspace investment could be recovered in 41 years.

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